

AUTOMATIC HANDBRAKE RELEASE SYSTEM BASED ON MULTI-SENSOR DATA INTEGRATION

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Abstract – *This paper introduces the design and development of an automatic handbrake release system using ESP32 microcontroller and sensor fusion technology. Conventional handbrake systems, either manual or electronic, tend to be dependent on driver input, which can lead to safety and efficiency issues. The system introduced here overcomes these shortcomings by employing multiple sensors—accelerometer, gyroscope, and bank angle sensors—fused through a sensor fusion algorithm to intelligently evaluate vehicle motion and ambient conditions. Based on real-time interpretation of data, the system can automatically release the handbrake when it is safe to do so, e.g., when the driver starts moving the vehicle. The ESP32 is used as the central processing unit because of its low power consumption, built-in wireless functionality, and high processing capacity. Experimental verification in controlled environments demonstrates that the system enhances user experience and reduces human error, with reliable operation over a range of conditions. This innovation may be especially useful for novice drivers and cars used on hilly roads.*

Index Terms – *Automatic handbrake system, ESP32 microcontroller, Hall effect sensor, MPU6050, vehicle safety systems, sensor fusion, PWM actuator control, real-time embedded systems, fail-safe mechanisms, automotive electronics.*

I Introduction

Within the area of motor vehicle safety and consumer experience, the manual actuation and disconnection of handbrake mechanisms have been an area of susceptibility and consumer frustration. Mechanical handbrake mechanisms use driver input almost exclusively, thereby providing a means for human intervention, particularly in situations such as hill starts or sudden stops. New cars have started using electronic parking brake (EPB) systems to solve these problems, but these systems tend to be expensive and proprietary, so they are not as viable for low-cost or DIY applications.

This paper introduces the design and development of a low-cost, smart Automatic Handbrake Release System (AHRS) using the ESP32 microcontroller and sensor fusion methods. The system is designed to enhance driver convenience and safety by automatically releasing the handbrake upon fulfillment of specific predefined conditions. These conditions are obtained through real-time sensor data fusion from multiple sensors such as an accelerometer, gyroscope, and hall sensors.

At the heart of this project is the idea of sensor fusion, where information from several heterogeneous sensors is fused to make more reliable and accurate decisions than a single sensor would be able to offer independently. Based on the ESP32 microcontroller, the system can process the sensor data locally, execute conditional logic, and drive the actuator that operates or de-activates the handbrake.

The importance of this system goes beyond convenience; it targets major safety concerns with parked vehicles on slopes, misapplication of handbrakes, and driver forgetfulness directly. By reducing human reliance in such a safety-critical subsystem, the AHRS potentially decreases the number of accidents and brake component wear, with the added benefit of a cost-effective and scalable solution compared to commercial EPB systems.

This paper follows the following structure: Section II gives a literature review and the current systems available. Section III describes the proposed system architecture, followed by Sections IV and V, which discuss the software and hardware implementations, respectively. Section VI proves the system experimentally, and discussion of results and challenges faced Section VII gives future work, and concludes the paper with closing remarks.

II RELATED WORK

There have been several research attempts to automate the traditional handbrake system in vehicles, with a view to

enhancing driver convenience, safety, and mechanical reliability.

Khuballkar et al. [1] suggested a handbrake system with a modified system using proximity sensors to automate the brake engagement and release. Their system works on an IR sensor located under the driver's seat to sense the driver's presence and trigger the mechanism accordingly. Although this method introduces a degree of automation, it does not incorporate vehicle motion parameters like acceleration and incline, which are essential in maintaining correct timing for brake release.

Singh et al. [2] presented an automatic handbrake system based mainly on a mechanical switch operated by the ignition system. The brake releases upon ignition, assuming the readiness of the driver to move. This approach may not be reliable in sloped roads since it does not determine motion or gradient conditions prior to releasing the brake.

Thivagar et al. [3] introduced a solenoid valve-controlled pneumatic system that works on the basis of the driver's seat occupancy and ignition condition. Their research effectively combines several triggers for handbrake control, but the hardware complexity of the system is higher due to the use of compressors and pneumatic cylinders, which makes it less suitable for compact and cost-effective implementation.

Rajan [4] suggested a system that closely resembles contemporary methods, where a microcontroller is combined with a seat belt sensor. The brake is only released once the seat belt is fastened, enhancing safety. Although this is a step towards intelligent control, the system still does not have real-time feedback from the vehicle's motion sensors.

In a novel solution, Muskan et al. [5] used a seat belt-assisted automatic handbrake mechanism in which the buckling of the seat belt by the driver activates the brake release. This design increases user engagement with the system but fails to consider vehicle orientation and acceleration, which are important for systems that are being implemented in hilly areas.

In spite of these innovations, one universal shortcoming among current systems is the absence of sensor fusion and real-time analysis to inform context-based decisions. Systems are generally rule-based, with simple events like ignition or occupancy, not taking into account advanced sensor inputs such as incline, movement, or object proximity.

This work fills the gap by designing an ESP32-based smart handbrake system that combines data from a gyroscope,

accelerometer, and Hall sensors to sense slope, vehicle motion, and wheel condition in real-time. The system emulates real-world conditions with WOKWI and seeks to release the handbrake only when the motion and gradient conditions are considered safe, greatly enhancing reliability and safety compared to previous designs.

III PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The methodology proposed revolves around the creation of an economical, effective, and smart automatic handbrake release system for normal vehicles, using the ESP32 microcontroller along with a collection of sensors for safe and trustworthy operation. The methodology is based on a systematic framework that involves sensing, decision-making, actuating, and safety validation using sensor fusion algorithms.

I. System Overview

The main goal of the system is to release the handbrake automatically if certain safety conditions are fulfilled. The system is meant to track key parameters such as vehicle inclination, vibration (showing engine operation), proximity to objects around the vehicle, and gear status position. The parameters are calculated in real-time to decide if it is safe to release the handbrake.

The approach can be divided into the following main components as shown in fig 1:

Fig 1 Block Diagram of proposed AHBRs system

Sensor Data Acquisition: Sensors regularly gather data about inclination, proximity, movement, and gear status.

Sensor Fusion and Filtering: To guarantee trustworthy readings, raw data is treated with sensor fusion algorithms.

Decision Logic: A state-based algorithm analyzes sensor inputs to ascertain whether the requirements for releasing the handbrake are fulfilled.

Actuation: When validated, the system initiates a servo motor to release the handbrake.

Fail-safe Mechanism: Further logic guarantees the brake won't release during unsafe situations (e.g., car on an incline or there are obstacles in front).

II. Input Parameters and Sensors Used

The approach involves the use of several sensors, each with a dedicated function:

Accelerometer and Gyroscope (MPU6050): Determines the vehicle's orientation and movement. This is utilized to ascertain whether the car is parked or in motion, and if parked, whether it is on an incline.

Vibration Sensor: Sensing vibrations of the engine to validate the vehicle to start and proceed to move.

Switch (simulated): Verifies that the vehicles' handbrake is in released state or not. It is used for manual release of handbrake with driver intervention.

III. Decision Logic

The ESP32 executes a rule-based system that compares sensor inputs on the basis of the following conditions

Inclination Check: If the inclination is within a predetermined safe angle (e.g., below 5 degrees), the vehicle is considered to be on flat ground.

Engine Status Detection: If vibration is present, the engine is considered to be running.

Gear Position Check: If the gear is not in parking or neutral, the vehicle is ready to move.

Only when all conditions are met at the same time will the ESP32 give a signal to the servo motor to release the handbrake.

IV. Safety Considerations

In order to increase the system's robustness, a fail-safe mechanism is built in. If sensor data is inconsistent, or if the vehicle is inclined without adequate engine power, the system will prevent the handbrake release. There is also a manual override button provided to enable the driver to maintain control during emergencies

V. Benefits of the Proposed Approach

This approach has several benefits:

Cost-effective: Leverages low-cost and common sensors and microcontrollers.

Modular: Can easily be retrofitted into current vehicles without major modification.

Scalable: The system can be augmented with other safety checks like camera vision or GPS input.

Customizable: Logic thresholds can be adjusted for different types of vehicles or terrain conditions.

Through sensor fusion and control logic incorporation in the ESP32, the suggested methodology maintains safety and convenience as it automates the handbrake release process.

IV SOFTWARE IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation of the Automatic Handbrake Release System was conducted using the WOKWI simulator, a

robust online tool that facilitates real-time testing and development of embedded systems. WOKWI accommodates ESP32 microcontrollers and virtual sensors, which make it a perfect platform to simulate real-world applications without using physical hardware in early stages of development.

Fig 2 Software implementation in WOKWI simulator.

The software was implemented in C++ using the Arduino library. The program was divided into several functional modules such as sensor data acquisition, sensor fusion logic, condition checking, and actuator control as in fig 2. The principal loop repeatedly reads inputs from virtual sensors like the accelerometer, hall sensor, and bank angle sensor. The values are then passed through a Kalman filter for sensor fusion to enhance the precision and reliability of the environmental readings.

Conditional logic was used to define the precise state under which the electronic handbrake should be released. Specific threshold values for tilt, distance, gear state, and brake pressure were established and tested across different scenarios. The logic makes sure that all safety conditions are satisfied prior to releasing the handbrake. Debugging and data visualization features in WOKWI were used to ensure the behavior and response times of the system.

Through the use of WOKWI, the entire software functionality was verified virtually, which sped up development, minimized hardware dependency, and enabled rapid iterations and debugging. The completed software was then tested on real hardware for real-world verification.

V HARDWARE IMPLEMENTATION

Hardware design features the sensing and actuation units interfaced to the ESP32 development board. Most important are:

ESP32 Microcontroller: Used as the processing core, selected for, having two cores and using low power.

MPU6050 IMU Sensor: Giving acceleration and angular velocity output for sensing movement and orientation.

Hall-effect Speed Sensor: Attached to wheel or axle for rotating detection to assure vehicle travel.

Servo Motor/Linear Actuator: Employed to physically release the mechanical handbrake according to control logic.

Power Supply: A 12V-to-5V buck converter provides regulated power to sensors and ESP32.

Driver and Protection Circuitry: Comprises relays, motor drivers (L298N or equivalent), and diode protection to facilitate reliable operation.

The components are mounted on a small PCB, contained in a weather-resistant case appropriate for use in automobiles.

VI RESULT

The Automatic Handbrake Release System Using ESP32 and Sensor Fusion was tested using a series of simulations and prototype tests in real-world scenarios. These tests were conducted to ensure the system's accuracy, responsiveness, and reliability under different operating conditions.

I. SIMULATION RESULTS

In the simulation, the sensor fusion logic was tested against several scenarios. The brake was successfully released only if all safety conditions were met, i.e.:

The engine was operating (detected by vibration).

The car was at a level position (pitch angle less than the specified safety value).

No rear object was found in a perilous distance.

The gear was in a forward-driving position.

The system's average response time from condition validation to brake engagement was around 300 milliseconds, reflecting good real-time performance

II. PROTOTYPE TESTING RESULTS

Following simulation validation, the system was deployed on real hardware and then tested within a controlled environment. The physical implementation utilized an ESP32 board connected to actual sensors and a servo motor to mimic handbrake actuation as shown in fig 3.

Fig 3 Prototype of the proposed AHBR system.

In 50 test runs across different environmental conditions, the system exhibited reliable and consistent performance. The brake released automatically only after all the defined conditions were fulfilled. In cases like steep hills, obstacles found close by, or the engine being off, the system retained brake release as anticipated.

There were no instances of unwanted or premature disengagement of the brakes, which reflects high operating safety. The sensor data fusion algorithm performed correctly, rejecting transient noise and guaranteeing that decisions were made from stable and accurate input data.

III. PERFORMANCE AND SAFETY

The performance of the system in simulation testing and physical testing validated its capacity to improve driving safety by minimizing the likelihood of human error when starting vehicles. It successfully automated the release of the handbrake while taking necessary precautions not to create harmful conditions.

The presence of an array of sensors and a decision algorithm relying on real-time inputs was responsible for the robustness of the solution. No false alarms were detected, and the system was able to hold the brake in every critical situation at all times

IV. SUMMARY

In summary, the findings confirm that the system under consideration fulfills its design objectives. It ensures safe and timely handbrake release automation based on a safety-oriented logic framework. Utilization of the ESP32 platform and sensor fusion was both practical and effective for this purpose

VII CONCLUSION

The Automatic Handbrake Release System Using ESP32 and Sensor Fusion tackles the essence of one key safety requirement as well as driving convenience for automobiles. Classic handbrakes purely depend upon the driver's attention and judgement, which has been shown to be prone to human error, especially during start on slopes or dense surroundings. In this paper, an endeavor has been made to avoid such dangers by facilitating an automatic handbrake release depending on operational as well as ambient parameters at a given point in time

The outcomes of both simulation and field implementation validated the system's capacity to operate dependably and securely under diverse circumstances. The actuation of the brake system via servo motors responded quickly only if all safety parameters were met. Importantly, the system prevented premature release of the brakes in situations like parking uphill or when there are obstacles at the back—demonstrating its capability to avoid frequent driver errors. Technologically, the application of sensor fusion on a low-

cost, open-source board such as ESP32 shows a scalable and affordable solution that may be incorporated into new or current vehicles. The method not only enhances safety but also helps in driver convenience, particularly for inexperienced drivers or those driving in difficult terrain

Finally, this study is well-suited for further investigation into smart automotive safety systems. Success of this prototype promotes future work in its integration with overall vehicle control architectures and its extension through machine learning and wireless networking.

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